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NOD2 control of Washc1.

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We used a heterologous HEK293 system to identify genes whose expression was controlled by the NOD2 inflammasome. We identified control of the Washc1 gene by wild-type human NOD2. A second related gene, Wash2C2, was also controlled by NOD2. Two major susceptibility factors for inflammatory bowel disease include NOD2 and ATG16L1. Washc1 was isolated as a NOD2/ATG16L1 co-regulated gene, indicating its function and control by NOD2 might be of relevance to IBD pathogenesis.